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FROM BEHAVIORAL ROLES TO DIGITAL FUNCTIONS: RETHINKING THE BELBIN MODEL IN DIGITAL AGE HR PRACTICES

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Abstract: *Digital transformation has radically changed the nature of teamwork: hybrid and distributed formats, asynchronous communication, platform-based HR systems, and algorithmic control prevail. In this environment, M. Belbin's classic model of team roles, developed for stable face-to-face teams of the 20th century, requires critical rethinking. The problem lies in the inertial use of the model without taking into account new realities—remoteness, fragmentation of responsibility, and the replacement of some behavioral functions with algorithms. The article assesses the limits of the model's applicability in the digital era, identifying aspects that remain relevant (idea generation, strategic thinking, balance of contributions) and areas of lost explanatory power (diagnostics in an asynchronous environment, static roles). A transition from fixed behavioral roles to dynamic functions **that** are context-dependent and integrated with HR analytics is justified. Belbin's model is viewed as a diagnostic rather than a normative tool, requiring methodological adaptation to the conditions of digital transformation.*

Keywords: *Belbin model, HR digitalization, team roles, digital teams, remote work, HR analytics, dynamic functions.*

Recent decades have seen an accelerated digital transformation of organizations, affecting not only technology but also the very architecture of teamwork. The spread of hybrid forms of employment, the growth of remote work, and the development of platform-based HR systems and digital monitoring tools have changed the way employees interact. Teams increasingly exist not as physical spaces of shared presence, but as a network of interfaces, tasks, and digital traces.

Under these conditions, the logic of role distribution, leadership, and responsibility is being transformed. Employee behavior is becoming less directly observable and is increasingly interpreted through performance indicators, digital profiles, and engagement metrics. Team management increasingly relies on algorithms and data rather than direct observation. This calls into question the applicability of classical models of organizational behavior developed within industrial or early post-industrial management logic.

Meredith's Team Role Model The Belbin model is one of the most widely used concepts in team building and development. It is widely used in manager training, personnel assessment, and project work. However, its application in the digital environment is often inert: roles are interpreted as stable personality traits, test results are integrated into HR platforms, and the model itself is used as a universal team diagnostic tool.

The model's initial assumptions were developed in the context of offline teams, relatively stable organizational structures, and observable behavioral interactions. In digital teams, behavior is often mediated by technology, communication becomes asynchronous, and responsibility is distributed between people and algorithms. This creates the risk of replacing real team dynamics with formal

digital profiles and KPIs, which can create the illusion of control without a real understanding of the processes taking place. A theoretical and practical gap arises between the classical behavioral model and modern organizational reality.

Meredith's Team Role Model Belbin's theory of collaboration emerged within the management paradigm of the second half of the 20th century, a period when organizations were characterized by relative structural stability, clear hierarchies, and predominantly face-to-face interactions between employees. Belbin's research, conducted as part of management experiments at Henley Management College, relied on observing the behavior of participants in collaborative work settings in physical spaces [1].

The organizational logic of the time assumed stable team composition, predictable work processes, and the dominance of direct communication. The behavioral approach underlying the model reflected a desire to move away from a rigid personality typology and toward an analysis of functional behavioral manifestations within a team. This represented a step forward from purely psychological tests, as the emphasis shifted to the individual's contribution to the collective outcome [2].

It's important to note that the model was developed in a non-algorithmic management environment. Team dynamics were captured through observable behavior, while leadership was demonstrated through direct interaction. Digital communication tools were absent, and performance measurement was not entirely quantitative.

The Belbin model is based on the idea that team effectiveness is determined not so much by the individual competencies of its members, but by the balance of behavioral roles they perform during their collaborative activities. A role, in this logic, is not a position or a formal function, but a stable behavioral tendency manifested in typical ways of responding, making decisions, and interacting with other team members [1].

Belbin identified nine team roles, grouped into three categories: action-oriented, thinking-oriented, and interaction-oriented. Each role describes a participant's distinctive contribution to the overall result—from idea generation and strategic analysis to process coordination and maintaining a team atmosphere. Furthermore, each role encompasses both strengths and acceptable weaknesses, emphasizing the model's rejection of the idealization of the "universal employee" [1,2].

A key feature of the concept is its dynamic nature: it assumes that a person can exhibit multiple roles, and their expression depends on the context and team composition. However, in practical applications, the model is often interpreted statically—as a fixed personality profile, which simplifies the author's original logic.

The model is built on the assumption that observable behavior is sufficient to diagnose a role, and that direct interaction allows for the identification of each participant's contribution. This assumption is becoming the subject of critical analysis in the digital environment, where behavior is increasingly mediated by technology, and contribution is recorded through metrics and digital traces rather than through direct observation.

The essence of the model is an attempt to explain collective effectiveness through behavioral diversity. However, transferring this logic to the digital age requires a reconsideration of the very understanding of the role—from a stable behavioral pattern to a context-dependent function manifested in changing organizational conditions.

Despite its historical context, the Belbin model possesses a number of enduring advantages that explain its long-standing popularity in management practice. First and foremost, its strength lies in its operationalizability: roles are described using clear behavioral logic and are easily translated into practical recommendations for team formation and development. Managers gain a tool to understand employees' contributions not only through formal functions but also through their type of participation in teamwork.

The second advantage of the model is its rejection of a rigid hierarchy of role values. No single role is declared "best" or "key"; team effectiveness is linked to balance, not the dominance of one

behavior type. This is especially important for project-based environments, where a diversity of approaches—from strategic thinking to meticulous implementation—promotes sustainable results.

The third strength is the universality of the underlying logic. The idea that teams benefit from behavioral diversity is supported by numerous studies in organizational behavior and cognitive psychology. The model provides a language for describing this diversity and thereby reduces interpersonal conflicts, shifting them from the realm of "personality differences" to the realm of functional contribution.

However, it's important to emphasize that these advantages are realized when the model is applied correctly—as a diagnostic tool for analyzing team dynamics, not as a mechanism for rigidly classifying employees. It's the balance between practical simplicity and methodological rigor that determines its sustainability in the modern management environment.

Digital transformation has changed not only work tools but also the very structure of teamwork. A modern team is increasingly less a stable group of employees physically located in the same space and included in a single hierarchy. The "presence team" is being replaced by the "interface team"—a distributed, hybrid, and often temporary configuration of participants interacting through digital platforms [7,8].

The first key characteristic of a digital team is remoteness. Participants may be located in different cities and time zones, and communication occurs primarily through instant messaging, video conferencing, and corporate platforms [9]. This reduces spontaneous interaction and increases the importance of formal communication channels. Behavioral manifestations become less directly observable and are more often recorded in digital traces—messages, comments, and tasks in trackers.

The second characteristic is asynchrony. Decisions are not necessarily made in real time; discussions are spread out over time, and participation can be fragmented. This transforms the dynamics of leadership and coordination: influence is determined not only by charisma and immediate presence, but also by the ability to structure information and manage task flows.

The third characteristic is the fragmentation of responsibility. In the digital environment, some functions are delegated to algorithms and platforms: systems automatically distribute tasks, record deadlines, and calculate performance indicators. As a result, a participant's contribution is assessed not only through collective perception but also through quantitative metrics [5].

The digital team represents a new organizational form in which behavior is mediated by technology, communication becomes intertwined, and human roles are intertwined with the functions of the digital infrastructure. It is in this environment that a re-evaluation of traditional behavioral models, including the Belbin model, is required, as the very nature of how team roles are manifested is changing.

One of the key characteristics of the digital age is the algorithmization of management processes. Modern HR platforms, task management systems, performance assessment tools, and analytical dashboards create an environment in which a significant portion of management decisions are based on data, metrics, and automated procedures [6].

Algorithmization manifests itself primarily in the standardization of performance indicators. KPIs, digital task trackers, rating systems, and automated deadline monitoring mechanisms set formal boundaries for employee behavior. Team dynamics are increasingly assessed through quantitative indicators—task completion speed, engagement levels, productivity metrics—which strengthens the focus on measurable results and reduces the significance of difficult-to-record behavioral contributions [5].

This has a direct impact on the distribution of roles within the team. The behavioral characteristics described by the Belbin model may become secondary to the functional requirements of the system. For example, the role of coordinator or "team worker" may be partially replaced by algorithmic mechanisms for task distribution and interaction control. At the same time, roles associated with data analysis, information flow management, and interpretation of numerical indicators gain importance.

Moreover, algorithmization creates the risk of reducing complex social dynamics to a set of formal criteria. This creates the illusion of complete control: if behavior is recorded in the system, it is explained and controlled. However, digital metrics reflect only part of the team's reality, leaving informal connections, emotional support, and creative interactions out of sight [1,6].

The algorithmization of management not only changes control tools but also transforms the very logic of team dynamics. In this environment, behavioral roles must be considered in light of the fact that some functions are redistributed between people and digital systems, and performance criteria become predominantly quantitative [5].

The digital environment has changed not only team structure but also the ways in which leadership is demonstrated and how members interact. While in the classic management model, influence was often based on personal presence, nonverbal communication, and charisma, in a digital team these mechanisms are partially losing their power. Leaders increasingly interact indirectly, but through interfaces—messages, tasks, regulations, and digital reports.

Communication is becoming mediated and fragmented. Much interaction occurs in writing, increasing the importance of structured thought and clear language. However, emotional cues and context can be lost or interpreted ambiguously. As a result, the way behavioral roles are expressed changes: initiative, support, or critical thinking are expressed less through live discussion and more through comments in trackers, edits to documents, and digital reactions.

Leadership is also transforming. Instead of charismatic influence, the importance of the ability to manage information flows, establish transparent rules of engagement, and ensure coordination in remote settings is increasing. Authority can be built on competence in using digital tools and the ability to interpret data, not just on personal qualities.

An additional factor is the digital footprint. Employee behavior is recorded in the system, from the frequency of communication to the speed of response. This influences the perception of roles: contribution becomes visible through activity metrics rather than through a collective sense of participation.

The transformation of communication and leadership is changing the conditions under which team roles are manifested. The behavioral patterns described in the classical model remain significant, but they are realized in a different environment—one that is mediated by technology, partially algorithmic, and less dependent on physical presence (Figure 1).

Transforming Team Dynamics
 in conditions of digitalization

Despite radical changes in the organizational environment, Belbin's model has not completely lost its explanatory value. A number of its principles remain relevant in digital teams, especially where human thinking and interaction remain key factors in effectiveness.

First, the idea of behavioral diversity as a resource for collective performance remains relevant. Regardless of the working format—in-person or remote—teams still require a combination of strategic analysis, idea generation, coordination, and implementation. The functions that Belbin described through the roles of "thinkers," "coordinators," and "doers" continue to manifest themselves, albeit in modified form. Even in a highly digitalized environment, algorithms do not completely replace strategic vision, creativity, or the ability to integrate diverse perspectives [1,3].

Secondly, the model remains useful as a tool for diagnosing team imbalances. Problems in digital projects are often associated not only with technical failures but also with a lack of certain types of input—for example, critical analysis or process structuring. Role language helps identify which behavioral functions are weakly expressed and require strengthening [7].

Third, the concept of "tolerable weaknesses" retains methodological value. In an environment of high digital transparency, the risk of striving for universal effectiveness of each employee increases. The Belbin model reminds us that strengths are inevitably associated with limitations, and it is their combination that creates team resilience [6].

The model remains relevant to the extent that it is used as an analytical framework for understanding behavioral contributions, rather than as a static classification of employees [2]. Its viability in the digital environment is not due to the immutability of roles, but to the recognition that the human factor continues to play a key role even in algorithmic organizational systems [5,10].

While some of its principles remain relevant, Belbin's model faces limitations in the context of digital transformation. These limitations stem not from flaws in the original concept, but from changes in the very environment in which behavioral roles are manifested.

First of all, the model's diagnostic accuracy is reduced in distributed and remote teams. Roles, in the classical sense, were identified through behavioral observation during face-to-face interactions. In a digital environment, a significant portion of behavioral manifestations is hidden behind interfaces and asynchronous communication. Chat activity or comment frequency don't always reflect actual contribution, and "quiet" participants can demonstrate high value through individual performance without exhibiting the typical behavioral markers of a role.

The second limitation is related to platform employment and hybrid work formats. Modern employees often participate in multiple projects simultaneously, temporarily joining different teams. In such circumstances, a role ceases to be a stable behavioral pattern and becomes a situational function, dependent on the task and context. A model oriented toward a relatively stable team composition has difficulty accounting for such fluidity [6].

The third problem is the confusion of role and function in the context of algorithmization. Some coordination and organizational tasks are transferred to digital systems. As a result, the boundary between the human role and the system function is blurred. For example, task distribution can be carried out automatically, which reduces the significance of the behavioral coordinator as a separate figure [5].

Finally, there's the risk of over-formalization. Integrating test results into HR platforms creates the illusion of a precise typology, whereas behavior in a digital environment is more variable and contextual. A role once defined may not reflect the employee's actual participation in a specific digital project.

The model loses some of its explanatory power where team dynamics are determined not only by interpersonal interactions, but also by the architecture of digital systems, asynchronous communication, and the high mobility of organizational connections.

One of the most significant threats to using the Belbin model in a digital environment is its formalization. What was originally conceived as a tool for monitoring live team dynamics is increasingly becoming a digital profile, embedded in the HR system and used as a stable employee attribute.

In digital practice, concepts are often subverted: a role is interpreted as a function, a test as an objective personality characteristic, and a one-time assessment as an immutable status. As a result, complex behavioral logic is reduced to a typological label. This is especially noticeable when

assessment results are integrated into platform HR tools, where a role can become part of the algorithmic logic for selecting tasks or forming project teams.

of pseudo-diagnostics arises. The presence of test results creates a sense of precision and scientificity, but an employee's actual behavior in a digital environment can differ significantly from the recorded profile. The context of tasks, the level of autonomy, the nature of digital tools, and the communication structure can radically alter the manifestation of behavioral tendencies.

An additional risk is the illusion of controllability. Even if a team is formally "balanced" by roles, this doesn't guarantee effectiveness in asynchronous and distributed environments. Algorithmic logic can emphasize measurable metrics while ignoring informal aspects of interaction, such as trust, support, or creative tension.

Without critical rethinking and contextualization, the model can degenerate into an HR ritual—formally correct but methodologically superficial. In the digital age, its application requires abandoning static assumptions and recognizing that a role is not the same as a function, and that a test is not synonymous with actual behavioral contribution to a specific team (Table 1).

Table 1 - Limits of applicability of the team role model in the digital environment

Area of analysis	Preservation of explanatory power	Partial applicability	Loss of explanatory precision	Methodological commentary
Idea generation	High - creativity remains a human resource	—	—	Behavioral logic is maintained regardless of the work format
Strategic thinking	High - the need for integration of views remains	—	—	Digital tools do not replace the strategic function
Team coordination	—	Partial - some of the functions are transferred to algorithms	With high automation	The role is shifting towards process design
Control and delivery of results	—	Partial - digital systems take over some control	With full algorithmization	The behavioral function is replaced by system logic
Team communication	—	Partial - the format of manifestation changes	In an asynchronous environment	Behavior is expressed through a digital footprint
Role stability	—	—	Low - roles become situational	A transition to a dynamic model is required
Role diagnostics	—	Partial - the test is supplemented by analytics	In formal typology	The test becomes a hypothesis, not a final conclusion.
Team balance	—	Partial - balance depends on the	In hybrid structures	The balance is dynamic in nature

		stage of the project		
Interpersonal conflicts	Partial behavioral nature is preserved	—	In digital conflicts	New forms of communication tension are emerging
The illusion of control	—	—	High risk in digital HR systems	Formalization creates pseudoscience

Adapting Belbin's model to the digital age is impossible without reconsidering the underlying assumption of contextual stability. In today's organizational environment, employee behavior is determined not only by personal inclinations but also by the architecture of digital tools, the type of tasks, and the degree of autonomy in decision-making. Role ceases to be a purely internal characteristic and becomes a function of the environment.

The first key parameter is the type of task. In digital project work, tasks can be creative, analytical, routine, or algorithmically structured. In creative and strategic projects, roles associated with idea generation and conceptualization remain highly significant. In operational digital processes, by contrast, behavioral variability may be limited by strict regulations and system rules. Consequently, the manifestation of roles depends on the nature of the activity, not just on individual profile.

The second parameter is the degree of autonomy. In conditions of high autonomy, employees independently distribute their efforts, take initiative, and determine the methods of interaction. Here, behavioral roles become more pronounced. In conditions of low autonomy, when tasks and deadlines are strictly regulated by the digital system, the space for role expression narrows, and differences between participants are smoothed out by algorithms.

The third parameter is the team's level of digital maturity. In mature digital teams, members understand the impact of tools on communication and are able to adapt their behavior to the specifics of the environment. In teams with low digital maturity, the technological environment can distort behavioral manifestations, creating false perceptions of engagement or leadership.

Considering the digital context requires a shift from a universal interpretation of roles to situational analysis. The Belbin model can retain its diagnostic value in the digital age only if a role is viewed not as an immutable employee characteristic, but as a variable dependent on the team's tasks, autonomy, and technological infrastructure.

Adapting the Belbin model to the digital age does not imply abandoning it, but rather integrating it methodologically with modern HR tools. With the development of HR analytics, talent management systems, and digital employee profiles, the role concept can be used more flexibly and contextually. However, such integration requires caution and a reconsideration of its application logic.

First, digital data can complement, but not replace, behavioral analysis. Metrics of activity, engagement, task completion, and communication intensity provide insight into the structure of an employee's participation in the team. However, quantitative indicators only reflect part of the reality. Their interpretation must be consistent with the content of tasks and the quality of interactions; otherwise, there is a risk of substituting formal indicators for behavioral contributions [4,5].

Secondly, digital profiles can be used as a dynamic observation tool rather than a fixed typology. Unlike one-time testing, the digital environment provides data in real time. This allows the role to be viewed as a fluid characteristic, manifesting itself differently across different projects. This approach reduces the risk of employee stigmatization and makes the model more flexible.

Third, integration with HR analytics must take into account the principle of context. A behavioral pattern may be effective in one team and destructive in another. Therefore, digital systems should support analytical support for management decisions rather than automated role assignment.

Integrating the Belbin model with digital HR tools is possible provided its diagnostic nature is preserved and its algorithmic rigidity is abandoned. Digital data can expand the model's analytical capabilities, but cannot serve as the basis for mechanically classifying behavior.

One of the key conditions for adapting the Belbin model to the digital age is to abandon the idea of a role as a stable and unchangeable employee characteristic. In hybrid and distributed teams, behavioral function increasingly depends on the project context, task structure, and participant configuration. A role ceases to be an individual's "property" and becomes a temporary function that can be performed in a specific situation.

In a digital environment, employees often work on multiple teams simultaneously, moving from one project to another. In one context, a person may act as an idea generator, while in another, they may act as a coordinator or implementer. This contextual role transition reflects not personal instability, but adaptability to the demands of the environment.

The shift to a dynamic understanding of roles is also linked to the principle of team antifragility. A team capable of redistributing behavioral functions depending on tasks and external changes demonstrates greater resilience to uncertainty. Role fixation can limit flexibility, whereas conscious role rotation enhances the ability to self-organize [8].

However, dynamism doesn't mean chaos. It's a systematic approach in which roles are viewed as resources allocated according to project goals. Digital tools can support this flexibility by providing data on the current distribution of tasks and employee participation levels [6].

Adapting the Belbin model to a digital environment requires a shift from a static typology to a process-based understanding of the role—as a temporary, context-dependent function that contributes to the achievement of a collective result (Table 2).

Table 2 - Operational model for adapting team roles to the digital environment

Adaptation condition	Indicators (measured parameters)	Evaluation method	Interpretation scale	Management decision
Contextuality of roles	Correspondence of role distribution to the type of project tasks	Comparison of task map and role structure	Low Match / Partial / High Match	Redistribution of functions across project stages
Level of autonomy	The share of decisions made without external approval	Analysis of regulations and digital logs	≤30% (low) / 30–70% (medium) / ≥70% (high)	Adjustment of the management architecture
Digital maturity of the team	Proficiency in digital tools; quality of digital communication	Competency audit + platform activity analysis	Basic / Developing / Advanced	Training or changing the format of interaction
Dynamic roles	Frequency of change of functional leadership in the project	Analysis of project phases and distribution of initiatives	Static / Moderately Flexible / Adaptive	Implementation of a role rotation mechanism
Correlation of role and outcome	Linking behavioral input to project KPIs	Correlation analysis of HR data	Weak / Moderate / Strong	Adjustment of performance criteria

Separation of roles and functions	The percentage of coincidence between the behavioral and the role description	Comparative analysis of profile and functionality	Full Match / Partial / Independent	Revision of the logic of task distribution
Level of algorithmization	Percentage of processes controlled by digital systems	Business process audit	≤40% / 40–70% / ≥70%	Rethinking the Role of the Coordinator and Analyst

Digital transformation doesn't eliminate the behavioral logic of teamwork, but it does create new functional nodes within the team. While Belbin's classic model described behavior in face-to-face interactions, modern practice demonstrates the emergence of roles specifically conditioned by digital infrastructure. This isn't about replacing basic roles, but rather complementing and transforming them.

One such role is that of a digital process architect. This team member structures workflows in digital systems, configures interaction logic in task trackers, and creates transparent regulations and integrations. Their contribution lies not only in organizational coordination but also in designing the environment in which other participants interact.

The second role is that of a data interpreter. In an algorithmic management environment, the team is faced with a large volume of metrics and analytical indicators. This necessitates a participant who can translate data into management decisions, see the dynamics of processes behind the numbers, and warn against the risks of the illusion of quantitative control.

The third possible role is that of a digital mediator. In distributed teams, communication often suffers from asynchrony and a lack of nonverbal cues. A digital mediator ensures consistency, prevents conflicts from escalating in an online environment, and supports a culture of interaction through interfaces.

It's important to emphasize that these roles are not strictly fixed positions. They reflect the functional needs of the digital team. Expanding the model involves incorporating these contextually determined functions into the analytical framework, allowing the concept to be adapted to the modern organizational reality.

Hybrid and distributed teams create a different interaction configuration than traditional offline groups. Members may be part-timers, work in different time zones, and juggle multiple roles simultaneously. Under these circumstances, the idea of an "ideal balance" of roles within a stable team requires reconsideration.

Firstly, in hybrid teams, the importance of situational distribution of functions increases. A role may be used episodically rather than continuously, depending on the project stage or the nature of the task. For example, during the strategic planning stage, the need for analytical and creative roles increases, while during the implementation stage, the need for structuring and control increases. This makes the role balance dynamic rather than fixed.

Secondly, distributed work increases the importance of self-regulation and digital discipline. In the absence of constant physical supervision, role expression is linked not only to personal inclinations but also to the ability to manage one's own time and information flows. Behavioral contributions become less directly visible and require additional transparency mechanisms.

Third, hybrid teams are often formed around a specific task rather than a stable organizational structure. This leads to roles being assigned based on professional expertise and digital competence, rather than purely on behavioral preferences. As a result, the boundary between role and professional function becomes more blurred.

In hybrid and distributed teams, the Belbin model can retain its analytical value if roles are viewed as variable functions within a project. Moving away from a rigid notion of an "ideal set of roles" allows for flexible use of the model, taking into account the temporary nature of team configurations and the specifics of digital collaboration.

One of the key conditions for the correct application of the Belbin model in the digital age is its changing status in management practice. In the context of algorithmic management, there is a temptation to transform the model into a normative framework: defining the "correct" set of roles, distributing them among participants, and considering the team balanced. This approach methodologically simplifies the original concept and reduces its analytical depth.

Belbin model was originally conceived as a tool for observing actual team dynamics, not as a template for an ideal structure. Its purpose is to identify which behavioral functions are dominant, which are lacking, and how this impacts team performance. In a digital environment, this logic becomes especially important, as formal performance indicators can mask real imbalances in interactions.

Diagnostic application involves analyzing "what's happening" in a team, rather than prescribing "how things should be." This means abandoning the rigid assignment of roles to specific employees and recognizing their fluidity depending on the context. A role is viewed as a manifestation of behavior in a given situation, rather than as a fixed label. Furthermore, the diagnostic approach reduces the risk of pseudoscientific typologization. Instead of using test results as a final conclusion, the manager views them as a hypothesis that requires testing in real-world interactions. In the digital age, the Belbin model can retain its practical value only if used as an analytical tool for understanding team dynamics. Transforming it into a normative standard or an algorithmic rule for distributing functions contradicts both the model's original logic and the principles of agile management in a digital environment (Table 3).

Table 3 - The logic of team roles in a digital environment

Analysis parameter	Classical logic of the model	Digital organizational environment	Management conclusion
Role basis	A persistent behavioral pattern	Context-sensitive function	The role is viewed as a variable rather than a fixed characteristic
Method of manifestation	Observed face-to-face interaction	Digital footprint, asynchronous communication	Diagnosis requires data analysis + meaningful context
Team balance	Static "ideal set" of roles	Dynamic redistribution of functions	The balance is assessed according to the project stage
Coordination	The human role of the coordinator	Partially algorithmic	The coordinator is shifting towards the digital process architect
Quality control	Behavioral scrupulousness	System checks and automation	Human control shifts to analytical interpretation
Idea generation	Creative individual activity	Collective digital collaboration	of facilitating digital interactions is growing
Conflicts	Interpersonal	Communication and interface	There is a need for a digital mediator

Role stability	Relatively constant	Project-temporary	A rotational role model is required
Diagnostic method	Testing + observation	Testing + behavioral data + analytics	The model becomes part of a broader HR analytics system
Risk of distortion	Personality typology	Algorithmic formalization	Role assignment cannot be automated without contextual assessment.

The digital age hasn't abolished teamwork, but it has changed its nature. A team is no longer necessarily a physically connected group; it is becoming a networked structure, functioning through digital interfaces, algorithms, and distributed areas of responsibility. In such a context, classic behavioral models require critical reflection rather than mechanical adaptation.

The analysis showed that Belbin's model retains methodological value in recognizing behavioral diversity as a factor in collective effectiveness. The idea of balancing contributions, complementary roles, and acceptable weaknesses remains relevant even in algorithmic management systems. However, the limits of the model's applicability become more apparent in the context of remoteness, asynchronous communication, and digital transparency of activities [1,2].

The main risk of current practice lies in the formalization of roles and their consolidation in digital profiles as immutable characteristics. This approach creates the illusion of controllability but reduces sensitivity to the real dynamics of the team. In a digital environment, a role cannot be viewed as a static label; it becomes context-dependent and temporary, manifesting itself differently in different projects and interaction configurations [7,8].

Belbin model is not outdated, but it is no longer self-sufficient. Its productive use is possible only if contextualized, roles are understood dynamically, and it is integrated with HR analytics tools without algorithmic rigidity [5,6]. Otherwise, it risks becoming a ritualistic element of HR practice [3]. However, when adapted, the model can serve as an analytical framework for understanding team dynamics in the context of digital transformation and high organizational uncertainty.

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